

Appendix

Article “Hypermediation functionalities in Digital Platforms for Collaborative and Social Interaction”

Appendix 1.

Tree of codes created with the support of WebQDA.

Appendix 2. The literature review: publications by title, name of the authors and year of publication, and mobile applications/platforms with hypermediation functions

Nº	Article/Book	Author/s and year	Mobile applications/platforms with hypermediation functions			
			Name	Platform Type	Activity field	Functionalities
1	“We can remember it for you”: Location, memory, and commodification in social networking sites	Drakopoulou (2017)	Facebook, Twitter, Tinder, Dodgeball, Grindr, Happn, Swarm, Yik Yak, Shout	SNS's (social network sites)	Tourism	Sharing contents (internal and external), (re)Posting/comments, Recommendations/suggestions, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets)
2	A parasite market: A competitive market of energy price comparison websites reduces consumer welfare	Antal (2020)	PCW (price energy comparison platforms)	Marketplace	Marketing, Entrepreneurship /business	Review
3	An emergent algorithmic culture: The dataization of online fandom in China	Yin (2020)	WeChat, WeiBo	SNS's (social network sites), Customer opinion sites	Marketing	Voting Polls, Sharing contents (internal and external), (re)Posting/comments, Recommendations/suggestions, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
4	Crowdsourcing platforms as devices to activate subjectivities: Narratives on digital precarity and freelance knowledge workers	Risi, Briziarelli & Armano (2019)	Zoopa, Twago, Starbytes, Bestcreativity, Gopillar	Crowdsourcing	Entrepreneurship /business	Recommendations/suggestions, Form, wizard or other filling process
5	Double learning or double blinding: an investigation of vendor private information acquisition and consumer learning via online reviews	Hu, Dow, Chong & Liu (2018)	Amazon	Marketplace	Marketing, Entrepreneurship /business	Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Review
6	Effects of Mobile Text Advertising on Consumer Purchase Intention: A Moderated Mediation Analysis	Hongyan & Zhankui (2017)	Amazon, Taobao, JD	Marketplace	Marketing	Algorithm to filter and display information according to the users preferences
7	Electronic word-of-mouth generation and regulatory focus	Sohaib, Akram, Hui, Rasool, Razzaq & Khan (2019)	WeChat, DianPing	SNS's (social network sites), Customer opinion sites	Marketing	(re)Posting/comme nts, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Review

8	Evolution of Consumption: A Psychological Ownership Framework	Morewedge, Monga, Palmatier, Shu & Small (2021)	AirBNB, Bird, Blue Bikers, Turo, Lyft, Uber, Rent the Runway, WeWork	Customer opinion sites	Marketing	Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Review
9	Influence of Platform Characteristics on Purchase Intention in Social Commerce: Mechanism of Psychological Contracts	Hussain, Li & Li (2020)	Witao	Marketplace	Marketing	Sharing contents (internal and external), Chat, (re)Posting/comments, Recommendations/suggestions, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
10	Introduction. Nature 2.0: New media, online activism and the cyberpolitics of environmental conservation	Büscher, Koot & Nelson (2017)	Facebook, Twitter	SNS's (social network sites)	Politics	Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc, algorithm to group content (e.g. hashtag)
11	Mobile communicating place and place-inscribed communicative mobilities: Shaping alternative consumer cultures in mobile media communication	Xie (2021)	WeChat, WeiBo	Message service, Customer opinion sites	Marketing	Sharing contents (internal and external), Chat, (re)Posting/comments, Recommendations/suggestions, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
12	Online arbitration model for Russia based on international practice of dispute resolution in e-commerce	Shaydullina (2020)	ODR (Online dispute resolution)	Customer opinion sites	Marketing	Sharing contents (internal and external), Chat, (re)Posting/comments, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
13	Online influence? Social media use, opinion leadership, and political persuasion	Weeks, Ardèvol-Abreu & De Zúñiga (2017)	Facebook, Twitter	SNS's (social network sites), Message service	Politics	Chat, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets), Message service
14	Online shopper engagement in price negotiation: the roles of culture, involvement and eWOM	Levy & Gvili (2020)	Facebook, eBay	Marketplace, Customer opinion sites	Marketing	Sharing contents (internal and external), (re)Posting/comments, Recommendations/suggestions, number of views/users
15	<i>O território como tecnologia de mediação urbana: a customização territorial dos aplicativos móveis</i>	Latrônico, Mattedi, Spiess & Reis (2019)	Onde tem tiroeio (OTT), AlertaBlu	Territorial customization application	Smart cities	Recommendations/suggestions, notification, bookmarking
16	Political engagement of social media users in Korea	Kim (2019)	Facebook, Twitter	SNS's (social network sites)	Politics	Voting Polls, (re)Posting/comments, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets)
17	Potential mediations of hashtags within transmedia journalism	Bicalho (2019)	Twitter	SNS's (social network sites)	Politics	algorithm to group content (e.g. hashtag)

18	Promoting cardiovascular health and wellness among African-Americans: Community participatory approach to design an innovative mobile-health intervention	Brewer et al. (2019)	Facebook	Developed for research purposes	Health and well-being	(re)Posting/comments, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
19	Surveillance and algorithmic culture in the new global regime of information mediation	Bezerra (2017)	Facebook, Google, Amazon, Apple, Netflix, Spotify	SNS's (social network sites), Marketplace, Streaming services	Health and well-being	Algorithm to filter and display information according to the users preferences
20	Temporality alignment: how WeChat transforms government communication in Chinese cities	Pan (2020)	WeChat	SNS's (social network sites), Message service	Politics	Sharing contents (internal and external), Chat, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
21	The economic value of information in the network society [<i>O valor económico da informação na sociedade em rede</i>]	Moreno (2016)	WeChat, WeiBo, Instagram, Google	SNS's (social network sites), Streaming services	Entrepreneurship /business	Sharing contents (internal and external), Content creation (e.g. videos)
22	The Effects of Online Trust-Building Mechanisms on Trust in the Sharing Economy: The Perspective of Providers	Li & Wang (2020)	Airbnb, Xiaozhu	Customer opinion sites	Marketing, Entrepreneurship /business	Sharing contents (internal and external), Chat, (re)Posting/comments, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc
23	The landscape of customer engagement in hospitality and tourism: a systematic review	Hao (2020)	Facebook, Twitter, WeiBo, Tripadvisor, Instagram	Customer opinion sites	Tourism	Recommendations/suggestions, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets)
24	The use of YouTube in the Catalan procés. Political communication through social media: Mediatized prosumers? [<i>El uso de YouTube en el Procés catalán. Comunicación política a través de los social media: ¿prosumidores mediatizados?</i>]	Ramírez (2019)	Youtube	Streaming services	Politics	Sharing contents (internal and external), (re)Posting/comments, number of views/users, "order by" function, Content creation (e.g. videos)
25	Training to self-care: fitness tracking, biopedagogy and the healthy consumer	Fotopoulou & O'Riordan (2018)	Fitbit	SNS's (social network sites)	Health and well-being	Sharing contents (internal and external), display of tracked/motivational information, profile creation
26	Understanding domestic social media use among Chinese college students under the framework of uses and gratifications	Pang (2018)	QQ	SNS's (social network sites), Message service	Health and well-being	Sharing contents (internal and external), (re)Posting/comments, Collaboration functions - Social groups, events, etc

27	Web 2.0: Is the museum-visitor relationship being redefined?	Pulh & Mencarelli (2016)	Facebook	SNS's (social network sites)	Tourism, Culture	Third-party promotion (e.g. avatar creation and slogan insertion)
28	When interchangeability between providers and users makes a difference: The mediating role of social proximity in collaborative services	Nguyen, Didi Alaoui & Llosa (2020)	AirBNB, BlaBlaCars, Home Away	Customer opinion sites	Marketing, Tourism	Recommendations/ suggestions, Scoring/rating (inc. number of likes/retweets)
29	When Plentiful Platforms Pay Off: Assessment Orientation Moderates the Effect of Assortment Size on Choice Engagement and Product Valuation	Mathmann, Chylinski, de Ruyter & Higgins (2017)	Amazon, Netflix, iTunes, Google Play, GrubHub, Seamless, Hulu	Marketplace, Streaming services	Marketing, Entrepreneurship/b usiness	Algorithm to filter and display information according to the users preferences

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